

P: ISSN No. 2231-0045
E: ISSN No. 2349-9435

RNI No. UPBIL/2012/55438

VOL.- XIII , ISSUE- IV May - 2025
Periodic Research

Spider Species of Family Oxyopidae from Siddharthnagar Uttar Pradesh, India

Paper Id : 20465 Submission Date : 2025-05-06 Acceptance Date : 2025-05-21 Publication Date : 2025-05-25
This is an open-access research paper/article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.16882505

For verification of this paper, please visit on <http://www.socialresearchfoundation.com/researchtimes.php#8>

Akhilesh Sharma

Associate Professor
Department Of Zoology
S.P.P.G. College
Siddharthnagar, Uttar
Pradesh, India

Abstract

Lynx spiders (Oxyopidae: Araneomorphae: Araneae: Arachnida) are found throughout India. A total of 96 species belonging to four genera of Oxyopidae have been documented across all states and union territories of India, with the exceptions of Nagaland, Daman and Diu, Dadra and Nagar Haveli, and Ladakh, of which 65 species (67.7%) are considered strictly endemic. However, among these, four species appear to be misidentifications or erroneous reports. The highest number of species recorded was 35 in Maharashtra, followed closely by 34 species in West Bengal, while fewer than 15 species have been documented in other states. No lynx spider species have been documented in Nagaland, Dadra and Nagar Haveli, or Daman and Diu, probably due to the absence of surveys in these areas, which highlights the necessity for thorough research in these regions.. This paper describes the spider species from the family Oxyopidae, specifically *Oxypes javanus* and *Oxypes shweta*. Therefore, comprehensive faunistic surveys for these spiders are essential throughout the nation, particularly in Siddharthnagar.

Keywords

Lynx Spider, Oxyopidae, *Oxypes Javanus* and *Oxypes Shweta*.

Introduction

Spiders commonly refer to arachnids classified under the order Araneae (Arthropoda: Chelicerata: Arachnida). The family Oxyopidae includes spiders known as lynx spiders. These spiders move swiftly over plants, jumping from one stem to another with agility that rivals that of true jumping spiders. Lynx spiders are active during the day. While they leave behind a dragline even when leaping, they do not utilize webs to catch their prey. Features that help distinguish members of this family include their unique arrangement of eyes, as six out of eight eyes are positioned in a hexagonal pattern. Their legs are notably spiny. The chelicerae possess both boss and scopulae, have flattened front surfaces, and the margins of their fangs are short and smooth, equipped with a single small tooth. The clypeus is high, being several times the diameter of the anterior median eyes (AME); the labium is prolonged and detached; the endites are lengthy and parallel, with the female's palp featuring a claw; and leg spines protrude at a considerable angle. The abdomen tapers to a rounded end at the back. These are among the most prevalent and numerous predatory arthropods found in terrestrial ecosystems globally. Their foraging behaviors and lifestyles are highly diverse across species. Ecologically, they play a crucial role by consuming around 400-800 million tons of prey, primarily insects, each year worldwide and also provide a food source for various carnivorous creatures, including birds, amphibians, lizards, snakes, shrews, mice, bats, fish, and other insects. India boasts a rich variety of species, offers a tropical climate with biodiversity hotspots, and possesses the manpower needed to carry out biodiversity assessments, yet the most comprehensive account available identifies only 1,864 species across 475 genera.

Objective of study

This paper outlines the spider species belonging to the Family Oxyopidae. It provides a description of the morphology of *Oxypes javanus* and *Oxypes shweta* to assist in their

P: ISSN No. 2231-0045
E: ISSN No. 2349-9435

RNI No. UPBIL/2012/55438

VOL.- XIII , ISSUE- IV May - 2025
Periodic Research

identification and conservation in their natural environment. The focus of this work is to redocument and illustrate the spiders collected from the designated area and to furnish identification keys for them.

Review of Literature

From the designated area, two species were identified: *Oxyopes javanus* and *Oxyopes shweta*. We extend our gratitude to Dr. Theo Blick, Hummeltal, Denmark, and a member of the editorial board of the World Spider Catalog, for his numerous suggestions concerning the distribution of Lynx spiders in India. Singh, R. (2021). Distribution of Sparassidae (Araneomorphae: Araneae: Arachnida) in India. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical & Life Sciences*, 7(3): 82-89. Singh, R. (2021). Faunal biodiversity of Tetragnathidae (Araneomorphae: Araneae: Arachnida) in India. *International Journal of Biological Innovations*, 3(1): 92-119. Singh, R. (2021). Faunal biodiversity of Lycosidae (Araneomorphae: Araneae: Arachnida) in India: An updated checklist. *International Journal of Zoological Investigations*, 7(1): 110-158. Caleb, J.T.D., and Sankaran, P.M. (2021). Araneae of India, version 2021. <https://indianspiders.in/> accessed on April 29, 2021. Sharma, A., Singh, G., and Singh, R. (2020). Faunal diversity of Liocranidae, Mimetididae, Miturgidae, Nesticidae, and Oecobiidae (Arachnida: Araneae) of India. *Serket*, 17(3): 270-283. Sharma, A., Singh, G., and Singh, R. (2020). Faunal diversity of Linyphiidae (Araneomorphae: Araneae: Arachnida) in India. *Asian Journal of Conservation Biology*, 9(2): 304-314. Sharma, A., Singh, G., and Singh, R. (2021). Faunal diversity of spider families Dictynidae, Dysderidae, Eresidae, and Filistatidae (Araneomorphae: Araneae: Arachnida) in India. *International Journal of Zoology and Applied Biosciences*, 6(1): 1-9. Singh, B.B., Singh, R., & Singh, G. (2020). Faunal diversity of Clubionidae, Ctenidae, Cybaeidae, Deinopidae, and Desidae (Araneomorphae: Araneae: Arachnida) in India. *Journal of Applied Bioscience, Lucknow*, 46(1, 2): 32-43. Singh, B.B., Singh, R., & Singh, G. (2021). Faunal diversity of spitting spiders (Scytodidae: Araneomorphae: Araneae: Arachnida) in India. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical & Life Sciences*, 7(3): 82-89. Singh, R., and Singh, G. (2020). Diversity of mygalomorph spiders (Arachnida: Opisthothelae) in India. *International Journal of Biological Innovations*, 2(2): 178-201. Singh, R., and Singh, G. (2021). Updated checklist of Philodromidae (Araneae: Arachnida) from India. *World Journal of Pharmaceuticals & Life Sciences*, 7(2): 129-139. Singh, R., Singh, G., and Sharma, A. (2020). Diversity of yellow sac spiders (Cheiracanthiidae: Araneae: Arachnida) in India. *Journal of Entomology and Zoology Studies*, 8(6): 118-126.

Methodology

The investigation was carried out for a period of April 2023 to April 2024 . Samples were taken at different randomly selected sites in district of northeastern Uttar Pradesh, Siddharthnagar (27°N - 27°28' N and 82°45' E to 83°10'E and covers a total area of 2752 sq. km area, is flanked by Nepal in the north, Mahrajanj in the east, Basti and SantKabir Nagar on the south, and Balrampur on the west,

Fig 1. Siddharthnagar (27°N - 27°28' N and 82°45' E to 83°10'E and covers a total area of 2752 sq. km area (Collection Site)

Most morphological features used for identifications can be seen under an ordinary dissecting microscope. The features of the male pedipalp are best viewed by removing the left pedipalp at the junction between the trochanter and the femur and viewed ventrally and were expanded to reveal obscured sclerites. Internal genitalia were prepared for examination by placing the dissected genitalia in 10% KOH solution for one hour at 50°C to dissolve soft tissue. They were immersed in 10% KOH for 30 minutes at 50°C, then placed in water until they had fully expanded.

All measurements are in millimetres (mm). The order of leg lengths is given in a four-digit sequence, longest to shortest (e.g., 4123). The size range given for each species represent the smallest and largest individual of each sex found in all specimens examined.

Sampling

Standard sampling protocols for spider collection were adopted in different selected sampling spots. The detailed descriptions of the collection techniques (Shirbhate and Shirbhate, 2017) are as follows :

(i) Sweep Netting (ii) Ground Hand Collecting (iii) Aerial Hand Collecting (iv) Vegetation Beating (v) Litter sampling (vi) Using Aspirator (vii) Pitfall traps.

Identification

The adult spiders were identified using available literatures (Pocock, 1900; Levi & Levi, 1968; Kaston, 1978; Proszynski and Zechowska, 1981; Tikader, 1980, 1982a, b, 1987; Tikader and Malhotra, 1980; Tikader and Biswas, 1981; Barrion and Litsinger, 1994, 1995; Cushing, 2001; Proszynski, 2003; Keswani et al, 2012). Details of body parts, such as pattern of eye arrangement, were examined using a dissection microscope or a binocular microscope, and identification features noted and sketched for each taxon following Barrion & Litsinger (1995) and Sebastian and Peter (2009).

Abbreviations used in systematics

AE - anterior eyes

AER-L - length of the anterior eyes

ALE - anterior lateral eyes

P: ISSN No. 2231-0045
E: ISSN No. 2349-9435

RNI No. UPBIL/2012/55438

VOL.- XIII , ISSUE- IV May - 2025
Periodic Research

AME - anterior median eyes

RTA - Retrolateral tibia apophysis

PTA –Posterior tibial apophysis

LE – lateral eyes

ME - median eyes

MOQ - median ocular quadrangle (area encircled by the AME and PME)

MOQ-AW - anterior width in the MOQ

MOQ-AW < MOQ-PW - MOQ is narrower in front than behind

MOQ-AW > MOQ-PW - MOQ is wider in front than behind

MOQ-L - length in the MOQ

MOQ-PW - posterior width in the MOQ

PE - posterior eyes

PER-L - length of the posterior eyes

PLE - posterior lateral eyes

PME - posterior median eyes

Gu - Promarginal guide tooth

Result and Discussion

Description:

Genus : *Oxyopes Latreille,*

Diagnostic characters: Posterior row of eyes strongly procurved. The distance between the posterior laterals, and the posterior medials or the anterior medials is about the same. The distance between the anterior medials, and the posterior laterals is also subequal. Prosoma high and convex, cephalic area slightly elevated, sloping sharply at the thoracic declivity and laterally. Face almost vertical. The lower margin of the chelicera has one tooth. Labium longer than wide. Maxillae exceed length of labium and converge on top of it. Abdomen elongate, widest behind base and tapering to the spinnerets. Legs very long, spinous, and usually with longitudinal gray bands in venter of femora, spines long and thick. Legs IV are longer than legs III.

From the target area, only two species of *Oxyopes* were recorded which can be identified by following key characters:

Identification of species of *Oxyopes Latreille*

Prosoma with two almost diverging longitudinal, black to gray bands below AME; abdomen brownish yellow tapering posteriorly with three or four diagonal gray bands dorsolaterally..... *Oxyopes javanus*.

Prosoma without bands below AME, with white chalky dorsum; lateral sides with longitudinal blackish line extending from base to end of abdomen; dorsum with minute net-like chalkwhite patches..... *Oxyopes shweta*.

Oxyopes javanus

Materials examined: 2 female, U.P.: Siddharthnagar: Chilhiya, 15.ii.2023, coll. Sushil Kumar; 1 male, U.P.: Siddharthnagar: Uska Bazar, 16.v.2023, coll. A. Sharma; 2 female, U.P.: Siddharthnagar: A. Sharma, 11.vii.2023, coll. A. Sharma; 3 male, U.P.:

Siddharthnagar: Barhni, 10.viii.2024, coll. Amit Singh; 2 female, U.P.: Siddharthnagar: Shohratgarh College Campus, 6.viii.2024, coll. A. Sharma; 1 male, U.P.: Siddharthnagar: Dhani, 10.viii.2024, coll. A. Sharma.

Description: Female (Fig.....A-C): Total length 9.43 mm. Carapace 3.41 mm long, 2.87 mm wide, 2.56 mm high. Abdomen 6.02 mm long, 2.33 mm wide, 2.90 mm high. Prosoma brown with grayish laterobasal margins, two almost diverging longitudinal, black to gray bands below AME, running downward to chelicerae, L-shaped gray band in the outer margins of clypeus above boss, broad yellow, V-shaped mark above the long, longitudinal brown fovea, black eye surrounds, and densely covered with brown hairs. Clypeus height five times diameter. Sternum yellow-brown with gray tinges, erect brown hairs with those at apical half longer than basal, lateral margins indented with outgrowths or extensions in between opposite coxae, posterior end tapers, extending beyond coxae IV, and apical end straight. Labium yellowish brown, longer than wide, with lateral midmargin indented, apical tip slightly indented at midpoint, and posterior end strongly rounded, height of labium 0.53 mm of maxilla length. Maxilla yellow, slender, and three times longer than broad, outer lateral margins with five or six long erect setae, serrula prominent and diagonal towards scopula. Chelicera same colour as carapace, banded gray dorsally (frontally), vertical, moderately robust, with two promarginal and one retromarginal teeth, fang short and relatively small, boss distinct. Legs brown, long, and slender, with long spines in all the segments except tarsi and black longitudinal band in the femora, tarsi three-clawed with one or two and 9-10 teeth in the inferior and superior claw, respectively. Leg formula 1243. Pedipalp yellow-brown with long spines, tarsus single-clawed with 7 teeth. Length of leg and pedipalp segments (mm) are given below:

Leg	Femur	Patella	Tibia	Metatarsus	Tarsus	Total
1	2.79	0.90	3.00	2.63	1.14	10.46
2	2.71	0.99	2.54	2.79	0.99	10.01
3	2.34	0.82	1.81	2.25	0.78	8.00
4	2.83	0.94	2.09	2.95	0.87	9.68
Pedipalp	0.87	0.43	0.65	-	1.02	2.97

Leg	Femur	Patella	Tibia	Metatarsus	Tarsus	Total
1	4.01	1.21	4.33	4.50	1.96	16.01
2	3.67	1.13	3.64	4.21	1.60	14.25
3	3.26	1.07	2.94	3.06	1.14	11.48
4	3.96	1.14	3.26	4.33	1.34	14.04
Pedipalp	0.83	0.41	0.63	-	0.97	2.84

P: ISSN No. 2231-0045
E: ISSN No. 2349-9435

RNI No. UPBIL/2012/55438

VOL.- XIII , ISSUE- IV May - 2025
Periodic Research

Abdomen brownish yellow and shaped as in the female, tapering posteriorly with three or four diagonal gray bands dorsolaterally. Spinnerets yellow-brown with a few gray marks, posterior pair as long as the anterior.

Distribution: India (Assam, Goa, Gujarat, Jammu & Kashmir, Karnataka, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Mizoram, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttar Pradesh, Uttarakhand, West Bengal), China, Indonesia, Japan, Java, Pakistan, Philippines.

Oxyopes shweta Tikader, 1970

Type : Oxyopes shweta Tikader, 1970. Records of the Zoological Survey of India, 64 (1-4): 1-83.

Abdomen long, narrowing behind, anterior mid-dorsally, with a lance-shaped brown patch; lateral sides with longitudinal blackish line extending from base to end of abdomen; dorsum with minute net-like chalkwhite patches. Ventral side similar chalk-white nets but middle provided with a longitudinal broad brown line extending from epigastric fold to spinners.

Distribution : India (Andhra Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Goa, Gujarat, Jammu & Kashmir, Karnataka, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Manipur, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Rajasthan, Sikkam, Tripura, Uttarakhand, West Bengal), China.

Discussion : The members of the family Oxyopidae has tapering abdomen. From the target area, only two species of Oxyopes were recorded. Legs very long, spinous, and usually with longitudinal gray bands in venter of femora, spines long and thick. Legs IV are longer than legs III which is very unique character of this species.

Conclusion Before this study no work was carried out about the Spider Species of family Oxyopidae from Siddharthnagar, Uttar Pradesh, India. A total of 96 Species of Spiders were recorded of which 65 species (67.17%) are considered strictly endemic with 6 different types of guild structure: Orb weaver, Stalkers, ground runner, foliage runner, space builder and ambushers

- References**
1. Singh, R. 2021. Distribution of Sparassidae (Araneomorphae: Araneae: Arachnida) in India. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical & Life Sciences*. 7(3): 82-89.
 2. Singh, R. 2021. Faunal biodiversity of Tetragnathidae (Araneomorphae: Araneae: Arachnida) in India. *International Journal of Biological Innovations*, 3(1): 92-119.
 3. Singh, R. 2021. Faunal biodiversity of Lycosidae (Araneomorphae: Araneae: Arachnida) in India: an updated checklist. *International Journal of Zoological Investigations* 7(1): 110-158.
 4. Caleb, J.T.D., and Sankaran, P.M. 2021. Araneae of India, version 2021. <https://indianspiders.in/> accessed on April 29, 2021.
 5. Sharma, A., Singh, G., and Singh, R. 2020. Faunal diversity of Liocranidae, Mimetidae, Miturgidae, Nesticidae and Oecobiidae (Arachnida: Araneae) of India.

- Serket 17(3): 270-283.
6. Sharma, A., Singh, G., and Singh, R. 2020. Faunal diversity of Linyphiidae (Araneomorphae: Araneae: Arachnida) in India. *Asian Journal of Conservation Biology* 9(2): 304-314.
 7. Sharma, A., Singh, G., and Singh, R. 2021. Faunal diversity of spider families Dictynidae, Dysderidae, Eresidae and Filistatidae (Araneomorphae: Araneae: Arachnida) in India. *International Journal of Zoology and Applied Biosciences* 6(1): 1-9.
 8. Singh, B.B., Singh, R. & Singh, G. (2020). Faunal diversity of Clubionidae, Ctenidae, Cybaeidae, Deinopidae and Desidae (Araneomorphae: Araneae: Arachnida) in India. *Journal of Applied Bioscience, Lucknow*, 46(1, 2): 32-43.
 9. Singh, B.B., Singh, R. & Singh, G. (2021). Faunal diversity of spitting spiders (Scytodidae: Araneomorphae: Araneae: Arachnida) in India. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical & Life Sciences*. 7(3): 82-89.
 10. Singh, R., and Singh, G. 2020. Diversity of mygalomorph spiders (Araneae: Opisthothelae) in India. *International Journal of Biological Innovations* 2(2): 178-201.
 11. Singh, R., and Singh, G. 2021. Updated checklist of Philodromidae (Araneae: Arachnida) from India. *World Journal of Pharmaceuticals & Life Sciences* 7(2): 129-139
 12. Singh, R., Singh, G., and Sharma, A. 2020. Diversity of yellow sac spiders (Cheiracanthiidae: Araneae: Arachnida) in India. *Journal of Entomology and Zoology Studies* 8(6): 118-126.
 13. Pocock, R.I. (1900). *The fauna of British India, including Ceylon and Burma. Arachnida*. London, pp. 1-279.
 14. Levi, H.W. and L.R. Levi (1968). *A guide to spiders and their kin. a golden nature guide*, Golden Press, New York.
 15. Kaston, B.J. (1978). *How to know the spiders. The pictured key nature series*. Win. C. Brown Co. Publishers. Dubuque, Iowa, USA, 1-272.
 16. Prószyński, J. and Zochowska, K. (1981). Redescriptions of the O. P.-Cambridge Salticidae (Araneae) types from Yarkand, China. *Polskie Pismo Entomologiczne*, 51: 13-35.
 17. Tikader, B.K. (1980). Thomisidae (Crab-spiders). *Fauna India (Araneae)* 1: 1-247.
 18. Tikader, B.K. (1982a). Family Araneidae (=Argiopidae), typical orbweavers. *Fauna India (Araneae)* 2: 1-293.
 19. Tikader, B.K. (1982b). Family Gnaphosidae. *Fauna India (Araneae)*, 2: 295-536.
 20. Tikader, B.K. (1987). *Handbook of Indian spiders*, Zoological Survey of India, Calcutta, India.
 21. Tikader, B.K. and Malhotra, B. (1980). *Fauna of Indian spider (Araneae)*, Vol. I, Thomisidae. *Zoological Survey of India*, 1 - 258 pp.
 22. Tikader, B.K. and Biswas, B. (1981). *Spider fauna of Calcutta and vicinity: Part-I. Records of the Zoological Survey of India, Occasional Paper*, 30: 1-149.
 23. Barrion, A.T. and Litsinger, J.A. (1995). *Riceland Spiders of South and Southeast Asia*. CAB International, Wallingford, UK, xix + 700 pp.
 24. Cushing, P.F. (2001). *Colorado spider survey*. Denver Museum of Nature and Science. Denver.
 25. Prószyński, J. (2003). *Salticidae (Araneae) of the Levant*.
 26. Sebastian, P.A. and Peter, K.V. (2009). *Spiders of India*. Universities Press (India) Pvt. Ltd. 614 pp.